

ACCIDENT DETECTION USING DEEP LEARNING UNDER BAD CC TV MONITORING CONDITIONS

Dr Subba Reddy Borra¹, Putchakayala Varsha Saisri², Ramini Arthi³, Thallada Harika⁴

1(Professor and Head, Information Technology, Malla Reddy Engineering College for Women, Hyderabad-500100
Email: bvsv79@gmail.com)

2, 3, 4 (Student, Information Technology, Malla Reddy Engineering College for Women, Hyderabad-500100.
Email: varshasaisriputchakayala@gmail.com)

Abstract:

This project will introduce and apply the Object Detection and Tracking System (ODTS) along with the well-known Faster Regional Convolution Neural Network (Faster R-CNN) for Object Detection and Conventional Object Tracking algorithm for automatic detection and monitoring of unexpected events on CCTVs in tunnels, which are likely to include (1) Wrong-Way Driving (WWD), (2) Stop, (3) Person out of vehicle in tunnel, and (4) Fire. To acquire Bounding Box (Bbox) results by Object Detection, ODTS accepts a video frame in time as an input. It then compares the Bboxes of the current and previous video frames to assign a unique ID number to each moving and identified object. This technique makes it feasible to follow a moving item in real time, something that is typically not achievable with other object detection frameworks. A dataset of event photos in tunnels was used to train a deep learning model in ODTS, which resulted in Average Precision (AP) values for the target objects Car, Person, and Fire of 0.8479, 0.7161, and 0.9085, respectively. The Tunnel CCTV Accident Detection System was then tested using four accident videos that included each accident, based on a trained deep learning model. As a result, the system has a 10-second detection time for all accidents. The more crucial point is that, as the training dataset grows in size, the detection ability of ODTS could be automatically improved without any changes to the programme codes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Finding the size and location of target items in still photos or moving movies has been made possible with the help of object detection technologies. Applications for self-driving cars, CCTV security systems, cancer detection, etc. have all become more prevalent. Another aspect of image processing that can be accomplished is object tracking, which involves tracking the positions of specified objects over time and performing unique identification. However, in order to track objects, it is first essential to establish object class and location in a static image that has been provided. Therefore, it can be claimed that the effectiveness of the object detection used should have a significant impact on the outcomes of object tracking. This object tracking technology has been effectively applied to a variety of tasks, including the tracking of a targeted pedestrian and a moving vehicle, accident monitoring in traffic cameras, monitoring of local crime and security concerns, etc. This research conducts a case study in the realm of traffic control about the analysis and management of traffic conditions by automatic object detection. These summaries are provided. A self-driving car's on-road vehicle detecting system reportedly has been created. This system recognizes a moving item and categorizes the type of moving object using a convolutional neural network (CNN). By adjusting the tracking center point in accordance with the

location of the detected vehicle object on the image, the vehicle object tracking algorithm tracks the vehicle object. The system then calculates the distance between the driving car and the visualized vehicle items, and the monitor displays a localized image from the perspective of a bird with the visualized vehicle objects. This system procedure makes it possible to view the location of a vehicle object objectively, aiding the self-driving system. As a result, it can pinpoint the vehicle object at the camera within 1.5 m of vertical and 0.4 m of horizontal tolerance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This stage involves analyzing the project's viability and presenting a business proposal that includes a very basic project plan and some cost projections. The feasibility assessment for the suggested system must be completed during system analysis. This is done to make sure the system isn't a financial burden for the business. Understanding the main needs for the system is crucial for feasibility analysis. The three main factors in the feasibility analysis are the economic viability, the technical viability, and the social viability.

Economic viability: this study is being conducted to determine the system's potential financial impact on the organization. The corporation is only able to invest a certain amount of money in the system's research and development. The expenses must be defended. Because the majority of the technologies

were freely available, the produced system was also developed under the budget. Only the individualized goods needed to be purchased.

Technical viability: this study is being done to evaluate the system's technical requirements, or technical feasibility. Any system created must not place a heavy burden on the technical resources at hand. The number of technological resources available will be heavily strained as a result. As a result, the client will face high expectations. The created system must have a low demand because its implementation merely necessitates little or no adjustments.

Social viability: the goal of the study is to determine how much the user accepts the system. This includes the instruction needed for the user to operate the system effectively. The system shouldn't make the user feel threatened; instead, they should view it as a need. The techniques used to inform and acquaint the user with the system are the only factors that affect the level of acceptance by the users. As the system's ultimate user, his confidence must be increased so that he may offer some helpful criticism, which is encouraged.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

The current approach uses a convolutional neural network to recognize vehicle objects and categorize them according to their types (CNN). By adjusting the tracking center point in accordance with the

location of the detected vehicle object on the image, the vehicle object tracking algorithm tracks the vehicle object. The system then calculates the distance between the driving car and the visualized vehicle items, and the monitor displays a localized image from the perspective of a bird with the visualized vehicle objects.

DISADVANTAGES

1. To identify the vehicle BBox, this system uses binary classification with SVM to derive a feature from the satellite image using CNN as an input value.
2. This system makes use of BBox, which was discovered through object detection in films or photos. The Gaussian Mixture Model and the algorithm applied to the system were contrasted.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the suggested system, an effort is made to create an object detection and tracking system (ODTS) with a yolo that can gather moving data of target objects with names by fusing object tracking algorithm with deep learning-based object detection process. It is believed that ODTS has received sufficient training to correctly detect objects in a given image frame. At the time interval c , ODTS receives a set of video frames, gains sets of coordinates, and detects n BBoxes. From the trained object detection system, BBox T of objects on the specified image frame at time T . The object

identification module simultaneously classifies each detected object BBoxT into its associated type or class ClassT.

ADVANTAGES

1. 1. A Faster deep learning model to train the yolo object detection model, R-CNN was employed.
2. 2. To create this object tracking module, the yolo object tracking model was introduced.
3. Regional Convolution Neural Network (R-CNN) with YOLO Model

MODULES

- Users
- Object Detection And Tracking
- Regional Convolutional Neural Networking
- Average Precision

DESCRIPTION OF MODULES:

USER

The system receives user input in this module in the form of a video. The output will be generated when this data has been processed using the yolo algorithm.

OBJECT DETECTION AND TRACKING

Classifiers or localizers are repurposed by earlier detection systems to perform object detection and tracking. They use the model to analyze an image at various scales and places. Detections are areas of the image's bounding box with high scores. To the entire image, we apply a regional convolution neural network. The image is divided into regions by this network, which also forecasts bounding boxes and probabilities for each region. The projected probabilities are used to weight these bounding boxes. Compared to classifier-based systems, our model has a few advantages. When testing, it considers the entire image, allowing the global context of the image to influence its predictions.

REGIONAL CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKING

R-CNN models first choose a few suggested regions from an image (anchor boxes are one form of selection method, for instance), and then label the categories and bounding boxes of those selected

regions (e.g., offsets). Following that, they undertake forward computation using a CNN to extract features from each suggested location. Then, we forecast the categories and bounding boxes of each proposed region using its attributes. Then, based on the information about the identified items, a dependent object tracking module is started to assign each of the detected objects a special ID number, IDt, and anticipate each object's subsequent location, BBOX. Tracking BBox u has a different number than tracking BBox n.

AVERAGE PRECISION

The training dataset's AP values for the target items to be detected show that cars represent the largest object class and have the highest AP values of all the classes. In other words, it was anticipated that the Car's deep running object detection performance would be quite trustworthy. On the other side, AP for Person object has a low value as a result of Person object. There is a small, long, tiny form. The AP of the Fire item was high, but because to the limited number of training examples, false detection for the object may be very likely.

V. RESULTS

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This research suggests a new method for ODTs that combines an object detection network powered by deep learning with an object tracking algorithm. It demonstrates how dynamic object information for a particular object class may be gathered and used. On the other hand, the performance of object detection is crucial since SORT, which is utilised in ODTs object tracking, only takes data from BBox and does not employ an image. Therefore, unless the object tracking technique is significantly reliant on object recognition performance, continuous object detection performance may not be as necessary. Additionally, an ODTs-based Tunnel

CCTV Accident Detection System was created. The experiments on deep learning object identification network training and evaluation as well as system-wide accident detection were carried out. This system also includes CADA, which makes decisions about each cycle based on dynamic data about the car's objects. It was feasible to identify the incidents within 10 seconds after testing with the image that contained each incident. However, deep learning training secured the object recognition performance of a trustworthy Car object, but Person displayed comparatively poor object detection performance. Due to the scarcity of Fire objects in the untrained movies, there is a high likelihood of false detection in the case of Fire. Securing the Fire image later should enhance the deep learning object detection network's performance in detecting fire objects. Although the ODTs can be used as an example of a Tunnel CCTV Accident Detection System, it can also be used in other industries that need to track the dynamic movement of a particular item, such as estimating vehicle speed or tracking illegal parking. Securing diverse photos as well as Fire and Person objects is required to improve the system's dependability. In addition, the system's dependability might be increased through application and ongoing monitoring of the tunnel management site

REFERENCES:

- [1] E. S. Lee, W. Choi, D. Kum, "Bird's eye view localization of surrounding vehicles :Longitudinal and lateral distance estimation with partial appearance," *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, 2019, vol. 112, pp. 178-189.
- [2] L. Cao, Q. Jiang, M. Cheng, C. Wang, "Robust vehicle detection by combining deep features with exemplar classification," *Neurocomputing*, 2016, vol. 215, pp. 225-231.
- [3] A. Arinaldi, J. A. Pradana, A. A. Gurusinga, "Detection and classification of vehicles for traffic video analytics," *Procedia computer science*, 2018, vol. 144, pp. 259-268.
- [4] K. B. Lee, H. S. Shin, D. G. Kim, "Development of a deep-learning based automatic tunnel incident detection system on cctvs," in *Proc. Fourth International Symposium on Computational Geomechanics*, 2018, pp. 140-141.
- [5] S. Ren, K. He, R. Girshick, J. Sun, "Faster R-CNN: Towards Real-Time Object Detection with Region Proposal Networks," in *Proc. Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2015, pp. 91-99.
- [6] A. Bewley, Z. Zongyuan, L. Ott, F. Ramos, B. Upcroft, "Simple Online and Realtime Tracking," in *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Image Processing*, 2016, pp. 3464-3468.
- [7] K. B. Lee, H. S. Shin, D. G. Kim, "Development of a deep-learning based automatic tracking of moving vehicles and incident detection processes on tunnels," *Korean Tunnelling and*

Underground Space Association, 2018, vol. 20, no.6, pp. 1161-1175.

[8] C. Dicle, M. Sznaier, and O. Camps, “The way they move: Tracking multiple targets with similar appearance,” in International Conference on Computer Vision, 2013.

[9] S. H. Rezatofghi, A. Milan, Z. Zhang, A. Dick, Q. Shi, and I. Reid, “Joint Probabilistic Data Association Revisited,” in International Conference on Computer Vision, 2015.

[10] C. Kim, F. Li, A. Ciptadi, and J. M. Rehg, “Multiple Hypothesis Tracking Revisited,” in International Conference on Computer Vision, 2015.